

Channel Marketing

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Abstract

In this invited paper, the imperative growth of the internet, efficiency of technology have impacted every industry. The different level of retailers must provide a competitive advantage to cope up with upcoming generations according to their taste and preferences. This may contain a need and importance for their well growth. The four levels of distribution of products make everyone in a comfort zone to receive their desirables. It contains several characteristics which highlight channel marketing. The only person who understands the tastes and preferences of a customer can make a wonderful output in his product and also makes a huge profit.

Introduction

A marketing channel is the organizations, people, and activities necessary to transfer the possession of goods from the point of production to the point of exhaustion. It is the way products get to the end-user, the consumer; and is also known as a distribution channel. A marketing channel is a useful tool for management and is crucial to building an effective and well-planned marketing strategy.

Marketing channels are the most complex phenomena encountered in the study of marketing. They encompass elaborate behavioral systems that usually involve many decisions makers and often extend over a wide geographical area. One aspect of the methods is their constants interaction they lead, there follow, they control, the conflict, they co-operate.

Definition of Channel Marketing

Dr. Philip Kotler defines marketing as “The Science and Art of creating, exploring, and giving value to satisfy the needs of a target market at a profit. Marketing knows unfulfilled needs and desires. It defines, types and quantifies the size of the identified market and the advantage potential. It pinpoints which segments the business is capable of serving best, and its designs and promotes the appropriate products and services.”

According to the American Marketing Association (AMA) Board of Directors “Marketing is the activity, set of organizations, and processes for creating, delivering, communicating, and exchanging offerings that have value for customers, clients, partners, and society at large.”

According to William J Stanton, “ A channel of distribution for the product is the route taken by the title to the goods as they move from producer to the ultimate consumer or industrial user.”

According to Cundiff, Still and Govani, “Marketing channel is the distribution network through which producers produce flow to the market.”

Channel Objectives

- To ensure the availability of products at the point of sale.
- To build the channel member loyalty.
- To stimulate channel members to put greater selling efforts.
- To develop managerial efficiency in the channel organization.
- To identify your organizations at the buyer level.
- To have an effective and efficient distribution system, to make your product and services available.

Nature and Importance of Channel Marketing

Few producers sell their goods direct to the final users. Instead, most use mediators to bring their products to market. They try to forget a marketing channel a set of interdependent organizations that help make a service or stock available for use or consumption by the consumer or business user. A company’s channel decisions directly affect all other marketing decision. Pricing depends on whether the company works with national premium chains, uses high-quality specialty stores, or sells directly to consumers via the Web. The firm’s sales force and communications decisions depend on how much persuasion, training, motivation, and support.

Thus, intermediaries play an important role in equalizing supply and demand. In making products and services available to consumers, channel members add value by bridging the major time, place, and possession gaps that divide goods and services from those who would use them. Segments of the marketing channel perform many key functions. Some help to complete transactions:

- **Information:** Gathering and distributing marketing research and intelligence information about forces and actors in the marketing environment needed for planning and serving exchange.
- **Promotion:** Developing and spreading effective communications about an offer.
- **Contact:** Finding and communicating with proposed buyers.
- **Matching:** Shaping and providing the offer to the buyer’s needs, including activities such as grading, manufacturing, assembling, and packaging.
- **Negotiation:** Reaching an agreement on cost and other terms of the offer so that ownership or possession can be transferred. Others help to fulfill the completed transactions:
- **Physical distribution:** Transporting and storing goods.
- **Financing:** Acquiring and using funds to satisfy the costs of the channel work.
- **Risk-taking:** Assuming the risks of carrying out the channel work. And a new item that has been added to the list of functions to be performed within the supply chain is environmental sustainability.

Types of Channel Marketing

The goods are when produced by the company it starts to move from Manufacturer to Wholesaler and maybe a Retailer or Consumer directly; this is depicted by the picture.

**Types of Channel Marketing Contains Four Sectors That are as Follows
Producer → Customer (Zero-level Channel)**

The producer sells the goods or gives the service directly to the consumer with no involvement with a middle man such as an emissary, a retailer, a wholesaler, an assistant, or a reseller. The consumer goes directly to the farmer to buy the product without going through any other channel. This type of marketing is most useful to farmers who can set the prices of their stocks without having to go for the Canadian Federation of Agriculture. Typically, goods are that employed by a smaller segment of the market influences producers and, therefore, goods that are provided in the response on the order of a few consumers are taken into account. Normally the goods and services of this channel are not utilized by large market segments. Also, the price of goods is subject to significant fluctuations.

Producer → Retailer → Consumer (One-level Channel)

Retailers, like Target and Walmart, buy the product from the manufacturer and sell them directly to the consumer. This channel works best for entrepreneurs that produce shopping goods like shoes, furniture, clothes, toys, and tableware. Since customers need more time with these items before they choose to buy them, it is in the best care of the manufacturer to sell them to another user before it gets into the hand of the customers. It is also a good plan to use another dealer to get the product to the end-user if the farmer needs to get to the market more speedily by using an established network that already has brand loyalty. By the form of the retail property, operators can be an independent business, owned by a different owner or to engage in the direct network. Mediators are essential and useful due to its professionalism, an ability to offer products to the target market, using their connections in the experience, industry, the advantages of specialization and the high quality of work. The fact suggests that manufactories produce general goods and products but limited in its assortment and merchandise. However, consumers seek broader collection in lesser quantities.

Producer → Wholesaler → Retailer → Customer (Two-level Channel)

Wholesalers, like Costco, buy the products from the producer and sell them to the customer. In this channel, consumers can buy stocks directly from the wholesaler in bulk. By buying the items in best from the wholesaler, the prices of the product are reduced. This is because the wholesaler takes away extra costs, such as service costs or sales force prices, that customers usually pay when buying from retail, giving the price much cheaper for the consumer. However, the wholesaler does not always sell directly to the consumer. Sometimes the wholesaler will go through a retailer before the product gets into the hands of the consumer.

Each dealer will be looking to make a decent profit margin from the product. So each time the buyer purchases the merchandise from another source, the price of the product has to increase, to maximize the profit each person will receive. This raises the price of the product for the end-user. Due to the simultaneous and joint work of wholesaler and retailer, a trade can only be beneficial if; a market is situated on a larger area, the supply of goods and products is carried out small but urgent consignments, it can be cost-effective and profitable by supplying bigger consignments to fewer customers. Industrial factories are in the seek of using benefits of mass production to produce and sell big lots while retailers look and prefer purchasing smaller consignments. This method for plants could lead to instant traffic, high efficiency, and cost-effectiveness.

Producer → Agent → Wholesaler → Customer (Three-level Channel)

This distribution channel involves more than one delegate before the product gets into the hands of the consumer. This salesman, known as the agent, assists with the negotiation between the manufacturer and the seller. Tools come into play when the farmers need to get their product into the market as quickly as possible. This appears mostly when the item is perishable and has to get to the market fresh before it begins to rot. At times, the agent will straight go to the retailer with the goods or take an alternative route through the wholesaler who will go to a retailer and then finally to the consumer.

Cooperation normally occurs when parties, in special, the last channel of marketing chain of distribution meet. Because producers, agents, retailers, and customers of this channel aid each other and benefit from each other. Their cooperation generates a greater output in terms of further profitability, by discernment and exploring newer markets of sales and building a better business relationship. The participants of distribution channels must have knowledge and experience not only for the effective maintenance of target segments but also to maintain the competitive advantage of the manufacturer.

Factors Determining The Choice Of Distribution Channels Marketing

Channel marketing contains some factors for the efficient transport of goods. Hence these four factors should be considered before deciding whether to opt for the direct or indirect distribution channel.

Market Characteristics

This includes the number of customers, their geographical buying habits, location, tastes and capacity and frequency of purchase, etc.

- Direct channels define where people could buy their products in their local area, which nearby for their convenient.
- In cases of consumers being geographically dispersed or residing in a different country, manufacturers are suggested to use Indirect channels.

The taste of the customers is also the choice of distribution of channels. If consumers expect to buy all their necessities in one place, selling through retailers who use product assortment is preferred. If control time is not an issue; if the demand isn't that high, the size of orders is large or if there's a concern of piracy among the consumers, direct channels are suited.

Product Characteristics

Product cost, perishability, technicality, and whether they are standardized or custom-made play a major role in selecting the channel of delivery for them.

Perishable goods like vegetables, fruits, and dairy products can't afford to use longer channels as they may perish during their transit. Producers of these goods often opt for direct or single-level channels of distribution. Whereas, non-perishable goods like toothpaste, soaps, etc. require longer channels as they need to reach customers who reside in areas which are geographically diverse.

The per-unit value of the product also decides whether the product is sold through a direct channel or an indirect channel. If the unit price is high like in the case of jewelry, direct or short channels are used, whereas products like detergents whose unit value is low use longer channels of distribution.

Competition Characteristics

The choice of the marketing channel is also affected by the channel selected by the competitors in the market. Usually, the firms tend to use a similar channel as used by the competitors. But some firms, to stand out and appeal to the consumer, use a different distribution channel than the competitors. For example, when all the smart phones were selling in the retail market, some companies partnered with Amazon and used the scarcity system to launch their smart phone as Amazon exclusive.

Company Characteristics

Financial strength, management expertise, and the desire for control act as major factors while deciding the route the product will take before being accessible to the end-user.

A company having a large number of funds and good management expertise sufficient can create the distribution channels of its own, but a company with low financial stability and management expertise has to rely on third-party distributors.

This picture depicts that the product, price, place, the promotion gives an extra attractive to a product.

Conclusion

The population of today's world has increases the buyers and sellers of the products. Regarding this, the middleman for transferring of goods from manufacturer to the consumers smoothly and they also make service after its delivery for certain products. The technology development in this decade made everything very easy.

In our view, the channel of distribution is very important for one company to get and maintain its reputation in public. Channel marketing determines the price of the product. And now, this may be controlled by Goods and Services Tax introduced by our Government.

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